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CONTINUOUS VAPORING PROCESSES IN NEW FILLED CONCRETE

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mamadov.boxodir85@gmail.com**ABSTRACT**

This article presents the results of experiments on the physical processes that occur during the hardening process of concrete in dry hot-climatic seasons and the reduction of their negative effects - as well as the physical and mechanical properties.

Keywords: dry hot climate, evaporation, plastic sinking, concrete care, ambient temperature, continuous evaporation

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada quruq issiq - iqlim mavsumlarida betonning qotish jaroyonida xosil bo'ladigan fizik jarayonlar va ularni salbiy ta'sirlarini kamaytirish – bartaraf etish masalalari va shuningdek fizik-mexanik xossalari to'g'risida tajriba natijalari keltirilgan.

Tayanch so'zlar: quruq issiq iqlim, bug'lanish, plastik cho'kish, beton parvarishi, atrof-muxit harorati, uzluksiz ravishda bug'lanish.

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье освещены физические негативные процессы в начальной период твердения бетона, а также физико-механические свойства бетона и результаты эксперимента твердеющего бетона в условиях сухого жаркого климата.

Ключевые слова: физические негативные процессы, пластическая усадка, уход за бетоном, интенсивные испарение воды, температура окружающей среды, температура окружающей среды.

The continuous evaporation of water from the concrete surface and, consequently, the occurrence of its "plastic sinking" depends on the rate of evaporation as well as the degree of binding to water and the degree of solidification, the transition to the crystalline state. In the experimental work, a concrete mix was used, taking into

account the water-cement ratio. The spread of the concrete mixture on the cone subsidence was 1-3 cm, and the following aggregates were used: Portland cement is a product of the Akhangaran factory brand M400, crushed stone is mainly a product of the Aktash quarry factory from local plants, crushed granules 5-20, quartz sand Mkr = 3, 4 at the level of demand. At the time of the experiments, the highest ambient temperature was 34–36°C and the relative humidity ratio averaged 37–32% [4.5].

RESULTS

The film coating was left at different distances from the concrete surface, thereby achieving its hermetic coating. During the experiment, one sample was compared across the surface, tightly closed, i.e. $\delta=0$ mm, and the remaining samples were solidified without any care ($\delta=\infty$). The graph of the relationship $j = f(\delta)$ obtained on the basis of the experimental results is shown in Figure 1 below. The curve 1 shown here is the amount of water that continuously evaporates from the freshly poured concrete, mainly depending on the thickness of the void layer when it is hermetically sealed. This, in turn, (j) for concrete, if the sample surface, if set in a dense state, differs insignificantly when $\delta=20-25$ mm and averages 0.043 and 0.072 kg /m²h (Figure 1). An increase in the void layer on the concrete surface leads to the occurrence of continuous evaporation from the concrete. That is, when the layer thickness is $\delta=60-65$ mm $j = 0,32$ kg/m²h, $\delta=200-205$ mm is $j=0,44$ kg/m²h. In this case, the rate of continuous evaporation from the concrete hardening in the open is about $j=0,99$ kg/m²h. Link to the results obtained:

$(\Delta l / l)_{\max} = f(j)$. As shown in Figure 1, this quantity $j=0,043$ and $j=0,072$ kg/m²h, can produce a small value $(\Delta l / l)_{\max}$, if $j \geq 0,32$ kg/m²h, the plastic deposition can reach a significant amount. , based on the results of their study and experiments on the plastic subsidence and continuous evaporation of concrete. In fact, we know that $\delta=0$ mm, $(\Delta l / l)_{\max} = 0,2$ mm/m and $\delta=20-25$ mm $(\Delta l / l)_{\max} = 0,45$ mm/m (Figure 1) [1.2.3.4.5].

Based on the results of the experiment, based on the 2nd curve shown in Figure 2, we can say that the final water loss rate in hardened concrete at $\delta=0$ and 20-25mm is between 3 and 5.5% of the total concrete water content, if $\delta=40-45$ mm $\Delta W/W=17...18\%$ it was observed that the dehydration rate continued. Thus, the thickness of the air gap between concrete and helioplasting is tightly closed around the perimeter of the surface, based on the results of experiments, taking into account the physical processes occurring in concrete, we determine that the thickness of the void layer is on average 20-25 mm. To determine this rule, we cast a sample-prism, put it under a 2-layer film coating for a day, changing the thickness of different cavity layers, part of the normally heated room part of the polymer film coating, tightly closed with

a surface part of the open polygon 28 and during the day we ensured that it hardened in the shop room. As a result, we determined their prism strength.

Figure 1. The amount of continuous evaporation in freshly poured concrete is -1; and water loss during recent continuous solidification ($\Delta W / W$) - 2; based on the indicators, a graph showing the dependence of the cavity on the concrete surface on the thickness of the layer

When the evaporation (dehydration) of the concrete is continuous $j \geq 0,32 \text{ kg/m}^2\text{h}$ is required, indicating that it continues to sink plastic, with the maximum amount being in the range of 1.75-2.77 mm/m. If the air gap layer is $\delta=40 - 45\text{mm}$, continuous evaporation in freshly poured concrete will be in the range of minimum and maximum critical values in the transition area, and as a result the maximum plastic subsidence value of concrete will be around 0.8 mm/m on average. Figure 2 confirms that the "plastic sinking" rate formed by the continuous evaporation of concrete is in direct contact. Based on the data of the experiments, we know that the maximum amount of "plastic sinking" of concrete varies slightly $j \geq 0,32 \text{ kg/m}^2$ per hour. This can be clearly seen when comparing Figure 1 [1.3].

This difference $(\Delta l / l)_{\text{max}}$ can be explained as follows: The difference from open concrete samples in direct contact with the environment is that continuous evaporation is directly related to the relative humidity in the environment, i.e., constant with wind speed and air temperature. will be. Therefore, mainly in dry and hot climates, the "plastic sink" side edges of the concrete barrier, the upper part of which is covered with a film coating, due to the effects of two physical processes: thermal expansion due to high temperatures under the film. Characterized by the occurrence of "plastic sinking" processes.

Figure 2. Graph of “plastic deposition” and evaporation (dehydration) of freshly poured concrete, which hardens under different conditions.

1. Tightly wrapped through polyethylene film; 2. Two-layer $\delta=20$ mm gap polyethylene coating; 3 Similarly, when $\delta=50$ mm; 4. Similarly, when $\delta=205$ mm; 5. In untreated concrete.

DISCUSSION

When installing the cavity layer on the concrete surface at different heights (thicknesses), the results of temperature measurements under the film coating showed that during the stabilization of the "plastic sink", ie every 3-4 hours after the sample is installed for testing, the cavity layer $\delta=60-65$ mm we know that the ambient temperature reached $t=63^{\circ}\text{C}$, $\delta=60-65\text{mm}$ at $t=63^{\circ}\text{C}$, $\delta=500-505\text{mm}$ at $t=55^{\circ}\text{C}$ The decrease in temperature in the solidification medium is due to the increase in the δ -layer, which in turn reduces the thermal expansion of the concrete sample several times. On the other hand, an increase in the void layer in the gap results in continuous evaporation of the concrete to water loss and consequent “plastic subsidence”. Therefore, by determining that the $(\Delta l / l)_{\max}$ ratio is an average of 1.75–2.77 mm / m, if the concrete film hardens under the coating, the thickness of the cavity layer is 60–65mm, 80–85mm, 200–205mm, respectively, and one that is not maintained. in concrete hardened under different conditions, it leads to the complete formation of their internal structure, the normalization of their strength and the violation of other properties [1.2.5].

CONCLUSION

Thus, the results of the study of the dehydration of concrete - increasing evaporation rate, continuous evaporation, plastic deposition, thermal expansion and its interconnection, the strength of hardened concrete under polymer film in different conditions and different voids - layer thickness show that the concrete surface the

thickness of the cavity layer, on average $\delta=20\text{...}25$ mm, does not significantly affect the internal structure of the physical processes occurring in the initial state of hardening concrete, if it is tightly sealed around the concrete surface [3.4.5].

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